

POLITICAL HISTORY OF FOUNDATION PROPERTIES MANAGED IN THE SOVIET PERIOD

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Annotation: this article describes the policy pursued against Muslim clerics and Islamic religious organizations during the years of Soviet rule and its consequences.

Аннотация: в статье описывается политика, проводившаяся в отношении мусульманских священнослужителей и исламских религиозных организаций в годы советской власти, и ее последствия.

Annotasiya: ushbu maqolada Sovet hokimiyati o'rnatilgan yillarda musulmon ruhoniylar va islom dini tashkilotlariga nisbatan olib borilgan siyosat va uning oqibatlarini yoritib berilgan.

Keywords: old method schools, new method schools, foundation lands, mosques, cemeteries, cemeteries, mutawalli, religious institution, priests, pilgrimage, Mahkamai Sharia, mudarris, madrasa, soviet school, religious sciences, religious beliefs, values.

Ключевые слова: школы старого метода, школы нового метода, земли фонда, мечети, кладбища, кладбища, мутавалли, религиозные учреждения, священники, паломничество, Махкамай шариат, мударрис, медресе, советская школа, религиозные науки, религиозные верования, ценности..

Kalitso'zlar: eski usul maktablari, yangi usul maktablari, vaqf yerlar, masjidlar, qorixona, mozorlar, mutavalli, diniy muassasa, ruhoniylar, hojixona, Mahkamai Shar'iyah, mudarris, madrasa, sovet maktabi, diniy fanlar, diniy e'tiqod, qadriyatlar.

Until the 20s of the 20th century, the activities of the old method schools continued in Turkestan and later in Uzbekistan. These schools, which have centuries-old traditions, were considered the main link in the way of literacy of the local population. Undoubtedly, the population of Muslim Turkestan, where religious beliefs and values are strong, paid great attention to the education of their children in religious schools, despite the propaganda of the Soviets. That is why the Soviets intensified their policy of sovietization of these schools. The issue of closing the old schools as soon as possible was a constant focus of the Soviet authorities. From the beginning of the 20s, under the guise of reforming these schools, the government began to pay special attention to Sovietization.

On June 20, 1922, according to the decree of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Turkestan "On the return of endowments to madrasas and mosques of the Republic of Turkestan", endowments belonging to old schools were returned.[1]

However, the VII Conference of the Communist Party of Turkestan, held on October 16-21, 1922, set the Soviet school the task of gaining a higher position compared to the old schools. To fulfill this task, Soviet schools will be supported in every way, and old schools will be deprived of any financial support in the coming years.

On October 22, 1922, the MIQ of the Turkestan ASSR passed a decision "On giving schools the right to teach religious knowledge", but this decision was not implemented consistently. At the meeting of the Presidium of the All-Union MIQ, the decision granting the right to teach religious knowledge to the Soviet schools of the MIQ of the Republic of Turkestan was canceled. As an exception and as a temporary measure, the teaching of religious knowledge was not prohibited only in the old schools in the part of Turkestan where Uzbeks are the majority and live together.

The Central Committee of the Turkestan Communist Party established a

control commission to review the decree on the return of endowments dated June 20, 1922. It was headed by U.EshonkhojayeV. This commission made the following proposals on November 11, 1922:

- the endowment lands belonging to mosques, shrines, and graves were returned to these institutions. Waqf spending is controlled by local waqf departments;
- correct and equal distribution of income is carried out by waqf bodies. Initial supply works should be carried out in new madrasahs and Soviet schools.

As can be seen from the decision of the Central Committee of the Turkestan Communist Party, the Central Committee of the Turkestan Republic submitted proposals to the Central Committee of the Turkestan, firstly, to change the procedure for using income from endowment properties, secondly, to change the management of endowments and establish endowment bodies, and thirdly, to reform old schools. Revenues from endowments and cultural institutions were supposed to go to reformed schools and Soviet schools.

On December 28, 1922, the Council of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Turkestan adopted the new decree No. 173 "On Endowments". According to it, before the October coup, the properties belonging to the foundations, mosques, pilgrimages, almshouses, graves, as well as charitable and cultural-educational institutions (madrasas, schools, orphanages, etc.) will be given to the relevant institutions.

Changes have been made to the management procedure of foundations. According to the new decree, the foundation organizations were managed by the General Foundation Administration. The management of waqf properties of mosques, madrasas and other religious organizations was managed by mutawallis. Trustees for madrasas, schools, orphanages and other religious charitable institutions are elected by the waqf department, and trustees of mosques and other religious institutions are elected by the local population, that is, the citizens of that neighborhood. On March 4, 1923, the Council of People's Commissars of the

Turkestan ASSR approved the "Regulation" on the ways and procedures for the implementation of the decree of the Turkestan MIQ adopted on December 28, 1922.

According to the "Regulations", the General Foundation Department consisted of organizational-informational, academic and financial-economic departments. The academic department managed madrasahs, schools, nursing homes, and was engaged in reforming old schools. According to the "Regulations" of the Council of People's Commissars of the Turkestan ASSR, the following tasks were assigned to the Academic Department: "a) to reform old-style schools, madrasas, to implement measures that meet new modern requirements; b) development of new program projects, measures to publish new educational literature based on them; c) training teachers who meet the requirements of the new program in cooperation with the People's Commissariat of Education and the General Directorate of Social Education; d) bringing mullahs, khatibs, judges, muftis to maturity in a revolutionary spirit; e) publication of magazines against cultural strata based on bigotry and other petty old-fashioned idiosyncrasies; f) activities that have an educational character and are being implemented are carried out in coordination with the responsible departments of the People's Commissariat of Education. [2]

Uyezd-shahar waqf departments are divided into three sub-departments: religious waqfs, organizational-informational, financial-economic. It was a department directed to spend the income from the endowments of religious institutions - mosques, mausoleums, shrines - for the reform and repair of madrasas and schools, as well as the construction of new schools. It was stated in the "Regulations" that "if the madrasa does not accept the program of the General Waqf Department, it will not use the resources of the Waqf".

In addition to many other tasks, the organizational information department is responsible for "reforming old schools and madrasas according to the instructions

of the General Foundation Department; j) the reformed new method of appointing teachers, mudarris to schools and madrasas; z) organization of modern training courses for teachers and teachers in cooperation with the department of public education; i) He set tasks such as "restoration of schools belonging to the local population, which were taken directly from the management of the People's Commissariat of Education".

Thus, the General Waqf Administration and its local bodies began to implement the tasks of discussing the issues of Waqf, financing the reform, construction and repair of new-style schools-madrasas and schools, and organizing cultural and educational activities among the population. . In particular, it was necessary to solve the issues of education, organization of pedagogical work, and leadership.

M. Okhunov was appointed as the chairman of the General Foundation Department, and Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, a leader in religious matters and a good understanding of foundation issues, was appointed as the head of the academic department. A number of waqf departments were established in the places. One of the primary tasks of the Waqf bodies is to reform old-style schools, and to fulfill this task, the academic department had to develop a program for reforming old schools.

At the meeting of the Presidium of the Turkestan ASSR MIQ on January 18, 1923, it was decided that the Turkish MIQ would gradually take over the new method schools, reform the old method schools, even partially, and bring them into the sphere of public education departments. It was recognized as the right direction. The issue of "Education Week" (School Strengthening Week) was also discussed at this meeting. In the "Regulations" that must be followed by the Central Commission for the organization of the Education Week, it is stated that those who graduated from a Soviet school have advantages over those who graduated from other schools in entering the public service and entering

secondary and higher educational institutions. It was indicated to carry out explanatory work on the fact that the students are exempted from local taxes.

In this list, much attention was paid mainly to the work of reforming old schools. As mentioned above, before the decree on endowments in 1920, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov spoke about reforming madrasas and schools. "Why is it necessary to reform madrassas and schools?" Munavvar Qori explained the necessity of reforms in this area as follows. In the Middle Ages, the Arabic language, logic, geography, astronomy, mathematics, natural sciences, Sharia, and Islam were taught in the schools and madrasas of Central Asia. Great scientists, philosophers, and professors grew up in such schools and madrasas. "The large observatory built by Ulugbek in Samarkand proves that science and culture were at their peak at that time," says Munavvar Qori.

On February 12, 1923, a meeting of the Tashkent city "Mahkamai Shariya" and Waqf Department offices was held. According to the decision No. 5 of the Republic of Turkestan MIQ issued on January 18, 1923 in connection with the "Educational Week" and the decision of the Executive Committee of the Old City on February 1, the reform of old schools and orphanages directly was assigned to the city education department. It is charged with the reform of schools, madrasahs, and religious institutions, and the direct financial support of the "Mahkamai Shariah" office for this process. In this decision issued by the executive committee of the old city, great attention was paid to teaching the students the "Quran" with "tajvid".

The conquest of Central Asia by the Russian Empire did not bring about any changes in the field of religious endowments. During this period, it was forbidden to open and repair new madrasahs and schools. The purpose of introducing such a policy was that madrasas and schools had a policy of teaching only religious knowledge and not teaching other subjects. Munavvar Qori opposed such a policy and suggested that it is wrong to teach only religious knowledge in madrasas and

schools, and to develop programs for the implementation of general education subjects in them. He put forward the idea of turning old schools into schools of the new method. In 1923, the head of the academic department, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, began to develop programs for the reform of schools and madrasas. The practice in this regard required reasonable, clear reforms. The archival documents show that already in the first stage of 1923, the reform program was developed and started to be implemented. Based on the new program, "5 madrasahs and 6 schools remain in the Tashkent foundation department. There are 14 schools with 440 students in Samarkand foundation department, 32 secondary schools with 1280 students in Khojand, 3 schools with 110 students in Kattakurgan. During this period, the number of schools of the new method was 60, and the number of students in them was 2580.

In the report dated October 16, 1923 of the Andijan Foundation Department to the General Foundation Department, information is given that the foundation department was established on May 19 and that Qori Boda was elected as its chairman. On September 4, 1923, 4 schools were reorganized here.

The old school reform program is kept in the archives of the Turkestan ASSR People's Commissariat of Education. This document is called "Short project of reorganization of religious schools (schools and madrasas) and the program of these schools for the academic year 1923-1924". The document was signed by Y. Aliyev, the deputy chairman of the General Foundation Department, and M. Abdurashidkhanov, the head of the academic department. The program was compiled by Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov and mainly consists of two sections. The first part is called "Reform of Schools", the second "Reform of Madrasahs".

There are subtle aspects of the reorganization of schools, which, first of all, require caution, otherwise public distrust and dissatisfaction with the new method of schools may appear. The reforms were initially carried out by the Tashkent Old

City Foundation Department. According to the information of the General Foundation Department on April 1, 1923, there were 15 primary schools and 4 reorganized madrasahs in Tashkent. The main foundation administration stated that the program of the Soviet school was introduced into all educational institutions under the authority of the Tashkent Old City foundation department, and the teaching of religious subjects was prohibited in the reorganized schools. Naturally, this would lead to the re-emergence of local people's discontent. In turn, the waqf department was not interested in the opinion of the teachers and parents. The people of the General Waqf Department supported this misconception. In his speech at the meeting of the People's Commissariat of Education of the Republic of Turkestan on April 12, 1924, the chairman of the General Foundation Department, M. Okhunov, said: subjects were taught. This program is temporary, and all schools in the Old city of Tashkent operate on the basis of the Soviet program. "There was no request from other foundation bodies to replace the existing program with the Soviet program."

M. Okhunov, the chairman of the General Foundation Department, took the wrong path and did not pay much attention to the schools of the new method. He mainly supported Soviet schools. In other cities and regions, the reform of old schools was carried out by the academic department of the General Foundation on the basis of the program. In 1923-1924 school years, local foundation bodies did a lot of work on school reform.

According to the statistics of the Syrdarya, Fergana and Samarkand regions, in 1917 there were about 1500 schools and kindergartens, and a large part of them, that is, about 80-90 percent, were supported by endowments. .

Since the establishment of Soviet power, the number of old-style (religious) schools has decreased sharply due to the decrease in endowment funds and other reasons. By the beginning of 1923, there were about 20 madrasahs and about 150 schools in the provinces , old schools remained, and the number of students in

them decreased significantly during this period. On average, 10-15 students studied in madrasahs, 8-12 students in schools and kindergartens. [3]

From the day of establishment of the General Foundation Administration, these schools have been reformed by transferring them to new method programs. The weight of social and humanitarian sciences and Soviet training in them was 40 percent. In this regard, 8 madrasahs and about 30 schools were reformed, the rest were closed, and nursing homes were removed from the provision of foundations. Their closure was caused by the fact that the buildings of many madrassas, schools and religious institutions did not meet the requirements of modern schools at all, and the need for a large amount of money for reconstruction.

From April 1, 1924, the reformed schools were transferred to the first stage of the program of public education single labor schools.

Local religious schools, madrasahs, and religious schools in the regions of Tashkent, Fergana and Samarkand did not operate at the expense of endowments, but this does not mean that the work of ending the old-style (religious) schools in Uzbekistan has come to an end. It is self-evident that schools were organized in mosques in almost all neighborhoods in all cities and villages, as well as in the houses of religious servants, mullahs, and imams, and most of the students in them were married teenagers. Due to the control of these schools and the inspectors of public education, the authorities themselves were powerless to fight against such old schools.

In the territories of the Bukhara and Khorezm People's Soviet Republics, religious and semi-religious mixed schools have been preserved, since no work has been carried out on the establishment of single labor schools.

Until October 1924, 105 schools were operating in the Old Bukhara region and Zarafshan region at the expense of endowments. Since October, the number of such schools has decreased, the new method program was used in only 30

schools, the number of students in them was 800, and the number of teachers was 38. The share of social sciences in the program of these schools was only 30 percent. There are 267 schools in Gijduvan, Karakol and Karmana districts, 124 of which operate on the basis of the new Khiva method program, where 2,400 students study and 150 teachers work. [4]

1500 old schools in Khorezm region were under the care of the mosque (neighbourhood). Many madrassas and religious schools operated in the USSR. According to the data of 1922, 89 madrassas were operating in all regions of the Republic, and they employed 189 mudarris, 101 imams, and 338 servants. 1395 students studied in madrasas. Only the waqf lands of these madrasas constituted 328,054 tanabs. In addition, there were many industrial and commercial endowment enterprises belonging to madrasahs. According to the data of 1924, there were 126 madrasahs in the USSR. The largest number of madrasahs was located in the city of Khiva, the capital of the former Khiva Khanate. By the end of 1924, there were 61 madrasahs here, of which only 45 were always functioning.

There were many slaughterhouses in Khorezm Republic, in 1922 there were 195 slaughterhouses in the USSR, and more than half of them were not working. The waqf land belonging to old houses was 35164 tanabs. By May 1, 1924, about 500 schools with 2,500 students were in operation. What is the reason for the slow emergence of new method schools? a natural question arises. On June 4, 1924, a partial answer to this question was found in the speech of the head of the General Foundation Department. In Khorezm People's Soviet Republic, there are 10 madrasahs and schools of the second level, 738 students and 73 employees are employed in them. There are 41 reorganized I-level schools with 3080 students. 123 employees served in these schools. In other documents, there is information that 10 madrasahs and more than 10 schools have been reformed in the Republic of Turkestan.

It can be seen that during the initial reform period, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, the head of the academic department of the General Foundation Administration, actively works in the field of school reform. In 1923-1924, it was planned to reform 40% of the old schools in the Turkestan ASSR. According to the academic department, there were 5,600 schools in colonial Turkestan with more than 70,000 students, but the reforms slowed down in 1923-1924.

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